

ADP – Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov (Social science data archive)

A bit of History, Present day issues
and Challenges in the future

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SEEDS Kick-off meeting, Lausanne, 4. - 6. May 2015

HISTORY

- Ljubljana school of empirical social research: Institute of social sciences in Ljubljana (from 60' , which means 50 + years of existence)
 - We started rescuing what remained of past research data
- Existence of strong on-going academic and government longitudinal data generation programmes (SJM, Youth, LFS)

Knowledge exchanges

- 90': Regular cooperation in international comparative research programmes was (re)established
 - Personal contacts and access to live experiences of a modern data archive organisation
 - E.g. ISSP, CSES project data processing requirements and support services offering

International Association for Social Science
Information Services & Technology

• CESSDA, IFDO and IASSIST support

- Mentoring role of CESSDA members (E. Mochmann, B. Hausstein)
- IASSIST conference participation (Outreach grants)

ADP established in 1997 as the Infrastructure research centre inside Institute of Social Sciences at Faculty of Social Sciences, UL

Consolidation (First decade)

- Scientific information / research infrastructure
Funding received from ARRS (Slovene research agency)
Data archivist staff professionalised
 - Permanent position, regular formal and on the job training
- Knowledge
 - Mastering of the technology of that time: DDI
- Good practice in established data service followed
 - Resulted in early application for membership in CESSDA
 - ADP joined CESSDA in 1998.

Further development

- Was part of CESSDA-PPP project (2008 – 2010)
- Continuous national funding secured

2008: [Call for proposals for infrastructural programmes for 2009 – 2014](#)

In 2014: [Call for proposals for infrastructural programmes for 2015 – 2020](#)

-includes final report evaluation for existing Infrastructure programmes

Additional funding possible for international research infrastructure funding, as stated in the *Plan of Research Infrastructure Development 2011-2020*

(e.g. CESSDA, Council of European Social Science Data Archives)

- Since 2012: 5 employees: ADP was accepted in a national [Research Infrastructures Roadmap 2011–2020](#)
- As of June 2013, the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA AS) is established as a permanent pan-European distributed research infrastructure that will provide full scale, integrated and sustainable data services. R Slovenia joined.
- ADP is national service provider fulfilling obligations of CESSDA AS

'Data publishing' metaphor

- Robust research data ecosystem needed
 - Funders' requirements clearly formulated in an open access national policy
 - Research data service is constantly seeking to show usefulness for data producers and users ---> investments in the research data infrastructure returns its value, if service is oriented towards high quality data, that has potential for long-term multiple use
- Cooperation in easing access to governmental data
- Research data considered as a high class scientific object
 - Archived data that meet the criteria are regarded as equivalent to scientific publications by ARRS

Current profile:

Social science data archive/service as national disciplinary research data centre:

- Acquire research data of high value and potential for secondary analysis
- Evaluation, assessment of research data offered
- Processing, quality check, metadata description
- Long-term preservation, curation with the purpose of permanent access
- Users are required to consistently cite data used
- Research data that are available in ADP catalogue holding count in research bibliography (personal and project scientific output)

Current situation

- We have more than 500 data sets descriptions in our holding
- Yearly around 600 users register for on-line access to analysis and download of data.
- 90 % students, 5 % researchers, faculty and other.
- Active promotion of data use (participate in teaching, guides, users training)
- Approx.. 100 depositors - academic and private research centres, individual researchers, commercial companies, governmental institutions.

Recent activities/ Involvement

- Close cooperation with Slovene NSI (DWB project and wider).
- Building capacity in digital preservation (one of key CESSDA requirement).
- Dedicated project delivered the [Proposal for an action plan on Open Access to research data in Slovenia](#) to the Ministry in 2003.
- Expert advice in drafting national open access policy addressing scientific results, including research data.
- Partner in SERSCIDA, SEEDS and H2020 projects

Advantages of existence of a developed and well established national social science research data centre

- Act as a prototype of developed research data infrastructure for other disciplines
- Development of expert knowledge in research data management and digital preservation
- ADP advice users and promotes further use of data

Similar national data services

- Cooperation established on a national level with the Humanities and linguistic research data infrastructure – CLARIN and DARIAH national partners
 - Archaeology data, history (History), ethnology (**DOKUMENTACIJA IN ETNOLOŠKI INFORMACIJSKI LABORATORIJ FF**, [Inštitut za slovensko narodopisje](#), **Audiovizualni laboratorij**), (ethno)musicology (**Glasbenonarodopisni inštitut pri ZRC SAZU**)
 - **Common language resources and Technology Infrastructure SI**, Slovenian corpora resources...
 - *See ŠTEBE, Janez; BEZJAK, Sonja. 2014. Nastavki odprtih podatkovnih zbirk kot podlaga za družboslovno in humanistično raziskovanje. Glasnik Slovenskega etnološkega društva, Slovensko etnološko društvo, 54 / 1,2, 8-16, Ljubljana, Slovenija (2014). (Open data collections prototypes as resource for social science and humanities research)*

CESSDA membership

National government is partner: Dr. Albin Kralj from the Ministry attends GA meetings

Ministry nominates national service provider

- National service requirements need to be fulfilled

CESSDA membership brings advantages

- A framework for cooperation in common activities and projects
- Important tasks for CESSDA AS are widening and strengthening of organization, already recommended by CESSDA PPP.

The purpose and the aim of cooperation with Statistical Office SORS

- one of Social Science Data Archives' missions is to provide quality microdata and metadata to different groups of data users: students, young researchers, registered researchers
- Forms of cooperation:
 - microdata: intensive work on deindividualized microdata, ready to be used immediately for statistical analysis using preferred software
 - microdata: preparing PUF files, later distributed by ADP
 - metadata: preparing structured metadata for researchers
 - activities to promote official statistics microdata scientific use

- Service provider – ADP as part of the University [infrastructural centre](#)
- Evaluation of received materials
- Bibliographic reference

Bibliografije raziskovalcev

2.20 Zaključena znanstvena zbirka podatkov ali korpus

40. ADAM, Frane, KRISTAN, Primož, VOJVODIČ, Ana, RONČEVIČ, Borut, KALČIČ, Špela, PODMENIK, Dane, LAMUT, Urša, BESEDNJAK VALIČ, Tamara. *RAZJED10 - Lokalna in regionalna razvojna jedra = [Local and regional developmental cores] : [datoteka podatkov]*. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov, [2010].

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/razjed10/>. [COBISS.SI-ID [29428061](#)]

kategorija: 2H (Z2); tipologijo je verificiral OSICD

točke: 3.75, št. avtorjev: 8

41. MAKAROVIČ, Matej, RONČEVIČ, Borut, TOMŠIČ, Matevž, BESEDNJAK VALIČ, Tamara. *Slovenski utrip 1/2010 : družba znanja*. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov, 2010. <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/sutr1001/>. [COBISS.SI-ID [1024194881](#)]

kategorija: 2H (Z2); tipologijo je verificiral OSICD

točke: 7.5, št. avtorjev: 4

- Potential expansion to areas that are less represented, including Quali-data, ethnology, economics, pedagogy, psychology, health etc.

Research data management planning (DMP)

DMP is a vehicle to secure **technical and legal conformance of research data in open access**, to avoid problems with data delivery into research data centre:

- Efficiency and quality in research data creation and documentation
- Ethical obligations
- Digital curation
- Planning for data deposit (where, how, what are the criteria for acceptance)

Modern research data policy considers DMP as required part of research project documentation and activity

DMP provides basis for claiming cost for additional efforts in preparing data and documentation for open access

New challenges: changes of policy

Research data Pilot (H2020):

-,Participating projects will be required to develop a Data Management Plan (DMP), in which they will specify what data will be open.,,
(Guidelines on Data Management in H2020, 2013, p. 1)

-,participating projects are required to deposit the research data described above, preferably into a research data repository,,(Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020, 2013, p. 11)

Guidelines on Open Access
to Scientific Publications and Research Data
in Horizon 2020

Version 1.0
11 December 2013

Guidelines on Data Management
in Horizon 2020

Version 1.0
11 December 2013

New promotional approach in 2012-2015

1) Target groups:

- researchers, librarians, decision-makers

2) Tailor-made seminars/workshops (partly supported with FOSTER project funding):

- Role of librarians in opening up research data and managing bibliography of researchers, June 18th 2014

(in cooperation with Central Social Sciences Library and Central Specialised Information Centre for Social Sciences)

- Open research data in the light of Horizon 2020 (2014, 2015, ongoing)

- Preparing research data for open access, Preparation, deposition, preservation, December 10th 2014

3) Targeted meetings to support preparing policies and infrastructure on institutional level (Universities):

- Faculty of Economics, University of Ljubljana (vice dean for scientific-research work and doctoral students, head of library), October 2014